

TEACHING TECHNIQUES FOR ADULT CLASSES USED IN PUBLIC SPEAKING

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Public speaking is the art of addressing a group of individuals, typically involves some degree of preparation. It may occur in familiar settings, such as family gatherings, or in front of unfamiliar audiences. Unlike presentations, public speaking often lacks significant interaction between the speaker and the audience.

Speeches serve various purposes, each aiming to achieve specific objectives. They can be persuasive, with the speaker seeking to sway the audience's opinion or secure their support, as in political campaigns. Alternatively, speeches may be informative, educating listeners about topics such as climate change and its potential consequences. Some speeches are purely for entertainment, like the humorous anecdotes shared during wedding receptions [2]. Others serve celebratory functions, such as announcing the recipient of an award. It's not uncommon for a single speech to fulfill multiple objectives simultaneously.

Teaching public speaking to adults requires a tailored approach that addresses their unique needs and challenges. Marjory North, a specialist consultant in public speaking, shared a thought on the Harvard Continuing Education blog that resonates with me and is worth discussing: the notion that practice does not inevitably lead to perfection [3]: “Good communication is never perfect, and nobody expects you to be perfect. However, putting in the requisite time to prepare will help you deliver a better speech. You may not be able to shake your nerves entirely, but you can learn to minimize them” [1]. That’s why we would like to share with you some numerous innovative techniques and methods exist to assist educators in teaching the art of public speaking effectively.

In order to catch and keep attention in sight, competent speech must obey the rules of oratory, regardless of the goals, composition and conditions of manifestation. Many students encounter challenges when initiating their work. Providing clear guidelines, such as specifying the type of public speech or assigning a particular topic, can alleviate this difficulty. Collaborative group work during the planning phase proves beneficial, fostering idea generation through mutual support.

Introducing diverse methods for brainstorming aids students in finding their preferred approach. Techniques like mind-mapping, list-making, or jotting ideas on post-it notes allow for individual preferences. These varied strategies empower students to organize their thoughts effectively, catering to different learning styles.

1. Structured Curriculum: Designing a structured curriculum with clear learning objectives and progressive exercises is essential for teaching public speaking to adults. The National Communication Association provides guidelines for developing public speaking courses that cover fundamental concepts, such as speech organization, audience analysis, and delivery techniques. A well-designed curriculum ensures that adult learners receive comprehensive instruction and have ample opportunities to practice their skills.

Examining Public Speaking Competency Standards NCA focused on two key texts: "Speaking and Listening Competencies for College Students" (Morreale et al., 1998) and "The Competent Speaker Speech Evaluation Form and Manual" (Morreale et al., 2007). These texts were selected due to their influence on curricular standards in Public Speaking education, particularly through their association with the National Communication Association (NCA). Public speaking curriculum, much like other institutionalized learning programs, is often shaped by the interests of those in positions of power. Renowned education expert Sir Ken Robinson highlighted the origins of the public education system, emphasizing its alignment with the demands of the Industrial Revolution and its resemblance to an assembly line [2].

2. Another important point is fluency and eloquence in language stand as the bedrock of effective communication. When delivering a presentation, few things can derail it as quickly as glaring grammatical or spelling errors. These mistakes not only distract the audience but also diminish the credibility of the speaker. Additionally, the overuse of filler words such as "um," "uh," or "like" can grate on the nerves of listeners, detracting from the message being conveyed. Thus, mastering the art of concise and precise speech is essential for captivating an audience. In the realm of oratory, clarity and correctness of expression serve as pillars upon which impactful speeches are built [**Ошибка! Залкада не определена.**].

3. Also adults must know the way of experiential Learning: According to research published in the International Journal of Public Leadership, experiential learning is an effective method for teaching public speaking to adults. This approach emphasizes hands-on activities, such as role-playing, simulations, and real-world speaking opportunities. By actively engaging in speaking exercises, adults can develop confidence, improve their delivery skills, and overcome stage fright.

4. Furthermore, cognitive-behavioral techniques, such as visualization, relaxation exercises, and cognitive restructuring, can help adults manage anxiety and build confidence in public speaking situations [4]. In their research article published in the Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing, authors Mary E. Shattuck and Patricia H. Hewitt highlight the efficacy of cognitive-behavioral interventions for reducing public speaking anxiety among adult learners. By addressing negative thought patterns and implementing coping strategies, adults can develop a more positive mindset and approach to public speaking. Establishing eye contact is crucial for effective communication. When addressing a room, speakers should aim to connect visually with every corner, though with sizable audiences, individual gazes become impractical. Unfortunately, many individuals, particularly students, tend to fixate on a single point or the instructor [3].

5. To refine this skill, a helpful exercise involves having each student deliver a brief 30-second introduction. Afterwards, attendees are prompted to raise their hand if they feel the speaker overlooked them. This exercise encourages speakers to diversify their visual engagement, enhancing their ability to connect with diverse audience members.

6. The potential for advance in public speaking will be integrating technology into public speaking instruction can enhance engagement and effectiveness for adult learners. Platforms such as Toastmasters International offer online resources, virtual meetings, and speech evaluation tools that facilitate remote learning and collaboration. Additionally, video recording and analysis software allow adults to review their performances, identify areas for improvement, and track their progress over time [3].

Moreover, in the end of this educated techniques teacher should provide adults learners with a constructive feedback and individualized coaching that is crucial to progress in public speaking. In the book "Teaching Public Speaking: An Instructor's Manual," authors George L. Grice and John F. Skinner emphasize the importance of personalized feedback in helping adults identify strengths and areas for improvement. Effective coaches offer specific, actionable advice and encourage learners to practice consistently to refine their speaking abilities.

In conclusion, teaching public speaking to adults requires a multifaceted approach that combines experiential learning, feedback and coaching, peer collaboration, structured curriculum, technology integration, and cognitive-behavioral techniques. By implementing these methods based on real sources of information and expertise, educators can empower adult learners to become confident and effective communicators in various personal and professional contexts.

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